

Recommendations Toward a Framework for Adoption and Use of Persistent Identifiers for Research Facilities, Platforms, and Instruments

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Introduction

The following recommendations toward a framework for adoption and use of persistent identifiers (PIDs) for research facilities and instrumentation are based on the activities of the “[FAIR Facilities and Instruments](#)” U.S. National Science Foundation (NSF) Findable Accessible Interoperable Reusable Open Science (FAIROS) Research Coordination Network (RCN) (NSF Awards 2226396, 2226397, 2226398). These recommendations were developed over the course of the project, which included three in-person RCN workshops in 2023, 2024, and 2025. Draft recommendations were discussed and refined by a variety of stakeholder groups in advance of the RCN’s final in-person workshop in Boulder, CO in September 2025 where the recommendations were vetted by the broader community and then finalized asynchronously after the workshop.

Background

PIDs are central to the vision of open science described in the [FAIR Principles](#). In recent decades, as open science has taken on greater visibility within scholarly research institutions, the use of PIDs has expanded significantly to encompass many purposes and resource types, including data sets, software, laboratory materials, physical samples, people, and organizations. PIDs have become a vital tool for enabling reproducibility, fostering collaboration, and facilitating access to scientific resources.

To take the next step in this progression, the FAIR Facilities and Instruments RCN focused on the assignment of PIDs to research facilities, platforms, and instruments.

¹ For full lists of participants in the RCN’s workshops who contributed to the development of these recommendations, see Appendix II in each of the following reports [CU Boulder in 2023](#), [FSU in 2024](#), and [NCAR in 2025](#).

Providing PIDs for scientific facilities, platforms, and instruments could increase transparency and enhance the discoverability of existing instruments, equipment, and data, in turn streamlining scientific research production and open science practices. PIDs also promise to increase the discoverability of existing research facilities and instrumentation, which may increase access to instruments and data and provide a mechanism for designating credit for scientific outcomes that derive from specific instruments, laboratories, technical staff, and funding agencies.

Funded by the NSF FAIROS RCN program, this project is led by a collaboration between the NSF National Center for Atmospheric Research (NCAR), University of Colorado Boulder (CU Boulder), and Florida State University (FSU). The project facilitated community-wide discussion and broad adoption of best practices that recognize the large variability in PID implementations. Key issues for this project cut across a number of concerns, including cultural, policy, institutional, and technical facets. Specific discussions included the 1) adoption of persistent identifiers for facilities, platforms, instruments, and related entities (e.g., data from instruments); 2) implementation of PIDs within technical infrastructure for instrument tracking and discoverability; 3) exploration of downstream impacts of instrument use and data generation; and 4) increasing transparency of research that is based on the use of research facilities, platforms, and instruments.

The project focused on developing recommendations based on best practices and areas of broad agreement emerging from the communities we engaged with across all project activities. Due to the scope and funding source of the project, these communities were primarily based in the U.S.; however, we did identify and engage with several prominent international efforts dealing with many of the same issues our project sought to address. Some of these efforts directly informed these recommendations while others were less relevant in the U.S. context. Similarly, some aspects of these recommendations may be useful for current and future related efforts in countries outside of the U.S. while others respond more exclusively to unique features of the U.S. research environment.

The primary way the project engaged with communities was by hosting three in-person workshops at [CU Boulder in 2023](#), [FSU in 2024](#), and [NCAR in 2025](#). Each workshop brought together 30-50 participants from academic institutions, national laboratories, nonprofit organizations, and private industry. Participants represented a wide range of research disciplines, including biomedical science, geological science, environmental science, space science, materials science, and more. In addition, participants' primary roles covered the range of stakeholder groups represented by the recommendations below, including facility and instrument providers, PID providers, academic publishers,

data repositories, data professionals, funders, and researchers. In addition to the three workshops, the project team also conducted focus groups with targeted stakeholders and presented on project progress at numerous meetings and conferences. The discussion and feedback the project team documented across all of these activities directly informed the development of these recommendations.

Definitions

Here we provide our working definitions of a number of key terms, drawing where relevant on already established resources. We emphasize that these definitions are provided to clarify the use of these terms within this set of recommendations, as we have found that there are no broadly agreed-upon definitions for many of these terms. Other definitions and related terminology might be employed across the research community to describe comparable concepts.

- Persistent identifier (PID) - Also known as a digital persistent identifier (DPI or digital PID), a PID is “a unique digital identifier that permanently and unambiguously identifies a digital object or an individual.” A PID is globally unique, persistent, machine actionable, and has an associated metadata schema.²
- Facility - A place that provides researchers with access to specialized instruments, platforms, and expertise to conduct their research. Examples include biotechnology laboratories, nanotechnology laboratories, and astronomical observatories. This definition also includes core facilities, shared facilities, shared research resources, and related terms.³ Some facilities are part of larger organizations (e.g., core facilities are part of universities) while others facilities are standalone organizations (e.g., government and national laboratories).
- Platform - An entity that might be a carrier or base for multiple instruments - e.g., a satellite that contains multiple instruments and generates multiple discrete data streams. Other examples include research aircraft, ships, uncrewed aerial systems, or ground-based systems that are deployed to collect varied types of data. For the purposes of these recommendations, networks of instruments are also included in this definition. An example of a network is a seismic network that has multiple instruments deployed on geographically different sites.

² National Science and Technology Council (NSTC). 2022. *Guidance for Implementing National Security Presidential Memorandum 33 (NSPM-33) on National Security Strategy for United States Government-Supported Research and Development: A Report by the Subcommittee on Research Security*. Joint Committee on the Research Environment.
<https://trumpwhitehouse.archives.gov/presidential-actions/presidential-memorandum-united-states-government-supported-research-development-national-security-policy/>

³ <https://sr.ithaka.org/publications/what-is-a-research-core/>

- Instrument - “A device used for making measurements, alone or in conjunction with one or more supplementary devices.”⁴ Instruments also include devices that collect and create data, create other types of objects, and process and prepare samples. Instruments may have configurations or settings that change over time or in relation to specific experiments and might need to be recorded in metadata. Instruments also need regular maintenance and calibration to ensure they continue performing correctly. Instruments can range in size, for example from small temperature sensors to more complex microscopes, X-ray MicroCT scanners, and RADAR and LIDAR devices.⁵

Recommendations for All Stakeholders

The following recommendations apply to anyone interested in or involved with assigning PIDs to research facilities, platforms, and instruments. These recommendations are intended to provide a general framework for standardizing adoption and use of PIDs for instruments, platforms, and facilities across disciplines and roles.

- First, identify the relevant use case - what is/are the main motivator(s) for assigning PIDs to facilities/platforms/instruments? Be as specific as possible, including all relevant actors and why they might use these PIDs. It is likely that there will be multiple use cases. The primary, generalized use cases identified by the RCN are:
 - Traceability/Attribution - Enable resources to be more easily tracked and acknowledged; enable citations and proper credit to be attributed to the people and organizations that contributed to a facility, platform, or instrument (e.g., facility/instrument providers, universities, funders, etc.).
 - Findability/Accessibility - Allow relevant audiences to find facilities, platforms, and instruments they might need for their own work; enable people to understand how to access facilities, platforms, and instruments (including any qualifications needed for access).
 - Provenance/Reproducibility - Establish provenance and other connections among facilities, platforms, and instruments and subsequent research data, findings, and other related resources. These connections and related metadata/documentation should enable people to reproduce findings and to assess whether different results could be due to instrumentation.

⁴ *International Vocabulary of Metrology. Basic and General Concepts and Associated Terms* (VIM 3rd edition, 2012). <https://www.bipm.org/en/publications/guides/#vim>

⁵ For the purposes of these recommendations, social science instruments (such as surveys) are not considered to be part of this definition. While PIDs may be valuable for these as well, many of the PID considerations for the types of instruments (e.g., physical objects) included in this definition do not apply to typical social science instruments.

- Consider what level of granularity of facility/platform/instrument PID assignment is necessary for the use case(s):
 - For the Traceability/Attribution and Findability/Accessibility use cases, less granular PID assignment is needed (e.g., a small number of PIDs assigned to high-level entities, such as facilities or instruments as a whole).
 - For the Provenance/Reproducibility use case, more granular PID assignment may be needed (e.g., more PIDs assigned to specific lower-level instruments and potentially to particular instrument configurations and components with versioning of PIDs to account for changes to instruments).
 - If multiple use cases apply, assign PIDs at all levels from the facility to the lowest level of instrument granularity needed.
 - For all use cases, also consider whether more detailed and structured metadata would better address the use case than assigning more granular PIDs.
- Include associated metadata for facility/platform/instrument PIDs:
 - In general, platform/instrument PID metadata should conform to the [PIDINST metadata guidelines](#) and be used to the fullest extent possible.
 - For the Traceability/Attribution and Findability/Accessibility use cases, which tend to apply more often to facilities and bespoke platforms/instruments, high-level metadata is likely sufficient.
 - For the Provenance/Reproducibility use case, more detailed platform/instrument metadata is necessary to include in PID and associated metadata (e.g., protocols, hardware configurations, dataset metadata).
 - If associated metadata is needed or available beyond what can be included in PID metadata, this should be provided by the responsible party (e.g., owner/provider of the facility or instrument), and be made available at (or linked from) the PID landing page using relevant community standards for the associated metadata.
 - Connections among related PIDs should be included in PID metadata whenever they exist. In many cases these connections provide added value (e.g., a PID for an instrument with links to PIDs in the metadata that identify associated articles, datasets, people, organizations, etc.).
- Understand PID governance and responsibility for assigning/maintaining PIDs for facilities, platforms, and instruments:
 - Identify who will assign and maintain the PID for the facility, platform, and instrument. Some aspects of this could depend on the governance

structure, policies, and procedures of the provider of the PID being used (e.g., DataCite DOI, RRID, ROR ID, etc.).

- If the entity responsible for assigning/maintaining the PID for the facility, platform, or instrument is not the same as the entity that operates/provides that facility, platform, or instrument, then determine how these two entities will communicate about the information needed for the creation of the PID as well as any changes to the facility, platform, or instrument that could necessitate changes to the PID and/or related metadata.
- Account for what should happen with PIDs if facilities, platforms, and instruments cease to operate or exist - “tombstoning” is a recommended practice where the PID continues to point to a landing page describing the facility, platform, or instrument and why it is no longer available. Responsibility for creation and maintenance of tombstone pages should be included in governance discussions.
- Identify which PID(s) to use:
 - Table 1 provides some major PID uses for instruments/platforms, facilities, and other connected entities. These recommendations are based on current practice and available PID system features (not necessarily technological or policy limitations) that the RCN identified over the course of the project. This is not an exhaustive list of PIDs, and some of these recommendations may not apply to all disciplines. Instead, the table provides guidelines for how to use some of the most prevalent PIDs currently in use in the US research community.
 - In addition to the PIDs listed in Table 1, the RCN surfaced ePIC Persistent Identifier Consortium for eResearch Persistent Identifiers ([ePIC PIDs](#)) and Archival Resource Keys ([ARKs](#)) as PIDs that could be used for instruments/platforms, but we did not find sufficient current use cases available in the U.S. research community to inform guidance on recommended use. All other relevant recommendations (e.g., for associated metadata) would still apply if using either of these PIDs.

Table 1. PID uses for instruments/platforms, facilities, and other connected entities

	Instruments and Platforms	Facilities	Other entities with connections to instrument/platform/facilities PIDs
Digital Object Identifier (DOI)	<p>Use DataCite DOIs for bespoke or unique platforms and instruments as well as for individually configured generic instruments that require a PID at the instance level.</p> <p>Example: NSF NCAR Integrated Sounding System (ISS) (DataCite DOI: 10.5065/d6348hf9)</p>	<p>DataCite DOIs are not appropriate for “facilities” (as defined in this document) as “facility” is not a resource type provided in the DataCite metadata schema. Some “platforms” (as defined in this document) might also be characterized as “facilities” by some research communities. If using DataCite DOIs for such entities, resource types such as “PhysicalObject” or “Service” could be used as appropriate.</p>	<p>Use DataCite or other (e.g., CrossRef) DOIs for articles, datasets, software, protocols, and other outputs associated with instruments, platforms, and facilities.</p>
Research Resource Identifier (RRID)	<p>Use RRIDs for generic instruments, with PIDs assigned at the model level, not individual instances of instruments. For some use cases, it could be valuable to use the RRID at the model level and concatenate it with a PID at the individual instance level as well as metadata to describe modifications and/or configurations that make the instrument unique.</p> <p>Example: ThermoFisher Scientific EVOS M5000 Imaging System (RRID:SCR_023650)</p>	<p>Use RRIDs for facilities that are part of a larger organization (i.e. core facilities part of a larger university).</p> <p>Example: Florida State University Chemistry and Biochemistry Nuclear Magnetic Resonance Core Facility (RRID:SCR_017380)</p>	<p>Use RRIDs for antibodies, model organisms, plasmids, cell lines, and other resources associated with instruments, platforms, and facilities.</p>
Research Organization Registry Identifier (ROR ID)	N/A	<p>Use ROR IDs for facilities that are standalone organizations (i.e. national laboratories).</p> <p>Example: Example: National High Magnetic Field Laboratory (ROR ID 03s53g630)</p>	<p>Use ROR IDs for identifying organizations that provide support for a facility, platform, or instrument as well as for identifying affiliations of people who are associated with a facility, platform, or instrument.</p>
Open Researcher and Contributor ID (ORCID)	N/A	N/A	<p>Use ORCIDs for identifying people who are associated with or use a facility, platform, or instrument as well as for tracking use of a facility, platform, or instrument by specific individuals.</p>

Recommendations for Specific Stakeholder Groups

Throughout the project, the RCN engaged with a number of different stakeholders who could be responsible for assigning PIDs to facilities, platforms, and instruments and/or playing critical roles in advancing adoption and use of these PIDs. The following recommendations are intended to provide initial steps people from various stakeholder groups can take to contribute to making facilities, platforms, and instruments more FAIR.

- Facility/Instrument Providers:
 - Identify roles responsible for assigning and maintaining facility, platform, and instrument PIDs.
 - Ensure appropriate PIDs (including associated metadata) are assigned at facility, platform, and instrument levels in line with use case and granularity needs as applicable (e.g., a core facility provider might ensure a PID is assigned at the facility level for attribution purposes and different PIDs are assigned at the platform/instrument level for reproducibility purposes).
 - Include instrument PIDs in dataset metadata and documentation for data generated, collected, and/or managed by facilities and the instruments they provide.
 - Encourage use of PIDs by researchers using facilities, platforms, and instruments.
 - Conduct regular communication with user communities about PIDs for facilities, platforms, and instruments. Communication should:
 - Be multifaceted and connected to regular communication methods (e.g., newsletters, trainings, user emails, delivery of data).
 - Provide consistent and easy to find recommended citations/acknowledgements that include PIDs
 - Communicate the value of using PIDs (e.g., “citations to our facility went up by X% after PIDs were implemented”).
- PID Infrastructure Providers (e.g., DataCite, RRID, ORCID, ROR, etc.):
 - Ensure interoperability among PID systems, for example the ability to explicitly designate relationships between PIDs.
 - Develop services that promote use and tracking of PIDs for facilities, platforms, and instruments (e.g., recommended citations, metrics for use of PIDs in publications).
 - Provide PID metadata options that align with the [PIDINST metadata guidelines](#).
 - Provide PID metadata options and/or guidance to enable machine-actionable identification of the type of entity to which the PID

refers (e.g., facility, platform, instrument) as well as to related entities (e.g., articles, datasets, software, people, organizations).

- Publishers:
 - Add guidance for where and how to cite facility, platform, and instrument PIDs in author guidelines.
 - Ensure PIDs for facilities, platforms, and instruments are cited in ways that enable automated harvesting and tracking across the published literature.
 - Align facility, platform, and instrument citation guidelines with other guidance related to datasets, software, and other resources to allow PIDs for all of these entities to be more easily connected.
- Funders:
 - Require or encourage funded facilities to assign and use PIDs at the facility, platform, and instrument level as applicable.
 - Require or encourage citing of PIDs when indicating to funders intended or actual use of facilities, platforms, and instruments in proposals and reports.
 - Include guidance for instrument, platform, and facility PID assignment in data management planning documentation such as Data Management and Sharing Plans and research infrastructure guides for new and existing facilities.
- Data Professionals and Data Repositories:
 - Ask researchers depositing data to repositories to provide information about the facilities, platforms, and instruments used in their research.
 - Ensure facility, platform, and instrument PIDs are included in dataset metadata and documentation wherever possible given repository capabilities. This could include existing metadata fields that allow for free text entry or related links as well as README text files (if used by the repository). Ideally, these PIDs should be made machine-actionable in DataCite DOI metadata and/or specific repository metadata fields whenever possible.
 - Promote use of PIDs for facilities, platforms, and instruments across home organizations by providing guidance to facility, platform, and instrument providers and researchers on how to acquire and use PIDs, how to encourage use and citation of PIDs, and what metadata to include with PIDs.
- Researchers:
 - Document usage of facilities, platforms, and instruments via PIDs whenever possible from experimental design to publication (e.g., in laboratory notebooks, protocols, dataset metadata, journal articles, etc.) to ensure proper identification and save future time and effort in maintaining

- links and metadata.
- Whenever possible, build research workflows that incorporate facility, platform, and instrument PIDs at the time data and metadata are being generated to allow PIDs and associated APIs to help automate metadata entry.
 - Look for recommendations from facility, platform, and instrument providers and publishers on how to cite facilities, platforms, and instruments using PIDs, and follow any recommendations as closely as possible.
 - Advocate for adoption of PIDs by instrument manufacturers - for example, including PIDs in file metadata produced by their instruments.

Conclusion

The “FAIR Facilities and Instruments” RCN’s recommendations provide a pathway for advancing the adoption and use of PIDs for research facilities, platforms, and instruments across all stakeholders in the research ecosystem. Due to the particular challenges and complexities with persistently identifying and tracking facilities, platforms, and instruments, work in this area must continue to evolve as best practices, roles, and responsibilities are further refined. Achieving broad success in this area is critical for enabling the shared goals of the open science community to enhance findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability of all research entities. These recommendations point to a framework that will enable such success given continued engagement by the RCN community and beyond.

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